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LG/LID: 674 Limbu

SOURCE(S): **Sources: van Driem, George. 1987. A grammar of Limbu. Mouton.**

Michailovsky, Boyd. syllable structure and combinational variation: voicing and gemination in Limbu. C.L.A.O. 1986.

Michailovsky, Boyd. On the phonology of Limbu r- and l- Handout for European Cooperation Project in Himalayan Languages: Zurich 1996.

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Revised Word Questionnaire (Oct 2003)

Depending on the structure of the language, you may need to consult the questions in a reversed order (e.g. look at stress patterns before looking at phonological rules of assimilation, etc.)

For assistance with terms you can consult Bickel's Programm und Verzeichnis der verfügbaren Materialien (on the server)

Or, refer to the .pdf version of the Bickel & Nichols chapter on inflectional morphology (<http://www.uni-leipzig.de/%7ebickel/research/papers/index.html>)

PHONETIC & PHONOLOGICAL QUESTIONS

You should note forms that the author overtly *describes* (and also covertly *treats*) as phonologically independent. I am especially interested in the *crucial* differences between what is possible (or highly common) within a phonologically independent unit and what is possible at the *edges* or across boundaries

As you investigate, make an inventory-style comparison of patterns/processes that apply to independent forms with both lexical content and grammatical content. Note what is possible within the form's internal boundaries versus what is possible at the edges (especially if the form is polysyllabic). For example, note possible and required consonant onsets at the initial edge of an independent unit, and compare these to the same onset patterns within the unit.

If an author says something like "no final consonants" or "no consonants in final position", always check to see if this constraint holds up at syllable edges *within* a phonologically independent form, and at the *ending* edge of the form itself.

Note also that a form may be phonologically "free" or independent, while not necessarily constituting a lexical category (i.e. "noun" or "verb" or "adjective"). I am especially interested in grammatical forms that are phonologically independent (and also lexical forms that are phonologically dependent upon something else—cannot occur alone phonologically, but they express a meaning that you might otherwise think of as "word")

Always take from the grammar at least 1 useful example of each thing.

Look for contradictory or conflicting phenomena (e.g. stress pattern A applies in

almost all cases except...). This may be important. In some larger phonological units, one criterion may apply, but the other may suggest a different organization of units.

1. Segmental & Phonotactic Patterns (edges vs. internal)

- occurrence of segments, limitations, prohibitions
- voicing, aspiration patterns
- manner patterns (plosive, affricate, fricative, tap, approx, etc.)
- place (either specific like bilabial, lamino-dental, or general like anterior, coronal, etc.)
- gemination
- vowel height/backness (quality)
- nasal vowels (see "rules")
- vowel length
- VV sequences (includes diphthongs)
- idiosyncratic, segment-specific restrictions or possibilities, like "no labiodental approximants at starting edge, even though they occur medially etc."

VD: no aspirated final C's, but yes in initial position

Yes, there are final voiced and voiceless C's:

lup 'leech'; ke:b 'tiger'; sendik 'night', but only final voiced is /b/ (unless loan from Nepali)

Many C's have restricted distribution:

s, never found syllable finally, but yes syll-init

ng never found syllable init, but yes final

aspirated C's never found syllable final, but yes syll init

alv nasal n never found word-finally, but yes wd-medial coda, and yes syll-init

C clusters--only found medially in onset position, never anywhere else

long vowels V: found word-finally and syll-final word medially

yes final /r/ (lamino-alveolar trill); pir 'suffering'

But there are no r-initial words unless they are Nepali loans and a few idiosyncratic cases (see below). vD says r is phonemic in C2 onset position. /l/ has an [r] allophone when in intervocalic position word-medially. But [l] occurs word-initially (and syllable initial if the prior syllable ends in any C except glottal stop).

l contrasts with a geminate ll, and this geminate does not show the alternation patterns with /r/ that non-geminate l does. Thus, the instrumental suffix -le has a geminate allomorph -lle that is used with definite referents. If the noun root syllable ends in a V, this -lle does not become -re, unlike what would happen if the suffix were -le.

Yes final glottal stop: sa? 'child'

w and j (approximants) found syll-initial, but never final (medial or word)

velar nasal not in initial position in Phedappe dialect, but yes syllable initial within the word

word-internally the following codas are found: k, ng, t, th, n, p ,ph, b, m glottal stop

no diphthongs unless with an affixed interrogative -i or a vocative -e. These do not consist of separate pwords, because they do not occur with an initial glottal stop (see the rule below about the role of glottal stop in words)

VV sequences within a word are not permitted, and are separated by epenthetic glottal stop (except for the two suffixes just above)

A V-only syllable does not take the glottal stop if it is adjacent to a consonant-initial

syllable.

2. "Rules" Part 1

Some phonological processes are restricted in application to the internal domain of a phonologically independent unit, and others are restricted to the boundaries/edges. Sometimes these differences are explicitly noted, others may be implicit. Please list the major processes that highlight such boundaries. Do these things happen to lexical forms only, to grammatical forms only, or to both?

Note types and locations of:

--vowel/consonant HARMONY/assimilation/dissimilation (note the types—place, manner, voicing, other)

--segment DELETION/epenthesis, any kind of insertion/deletion processes

--segment METATHESIS or any type of re-ordering

An assimilation rule that applies word-internally:

dental t, n > p, m / ___m,p

m-e-n-[ekot-m?na]-ha? > ekopm?na

another assimilation appears to happen at morpheme boundaries, but not sure if this applies across word boundaries:

m > ng / ng ___

hang-m?na > hang-ng?na

(there is also an m > n with same conditioning environments, but again, not sure of x-word boundaries)

this next assimilation appears to operate across word-boundaries:

+plosive > ~voice / ~ voice # ___

so thi: # dhungma? > thi: # thungma?

beer # drink

and it also happen across syllables and morphemes within a word, so it seems to be a syllable voicing assim feature, not a word or foot-based feature.

native plosives do not have voicing distinctions, and this doesn't appear to happen internally across syllable or morpheme boundaries, based on word lists and other formations that I've looked at in this grammar

vD describes syllable template as minimally V, but the possible structure is:

(C1)(C2glide)V(C3)

He says a syllable may also consist of minimally a vocalic nasal.

From the looks of the glossary however, the (C)(C)V syllable does not equal the word--most independent forms are at least CV: or CVC, which suggests a kind of minimal weight restriction on words. Most words are disyllabic (and perhaps bimorphemic?)

There are 1 or 2 particles that are CV: go 'then' (o= open back vowel), lja 'interjection'

It also looks like words prefer some kind of onset and do not like to be "V-only". I have found one word ('hair") that is v-only. van Driem describes a cue to phonological word in Limbu that he calls "glottal hiatus":

the glottal stop occurs before a vowel at the word-initial boundary (#_V)

and intervocalically within a word (#V_V#) to prevent diphthongization. It looks like

the glottal marks almost all V-V morpheme boundaries (with the exception of the 2 affixes mentioned above).

an example:

hi + -a + -e: + -s + -E + -tchu

hi?a?e:setchu

and some other examples that vD presents (ng = velar nasal; ? = glottal stop)

junge 'he sat down' (1 pword)

jung?e 'I'm sitting' (2 pwords--jung + e)

junge? 'sit down!' (1 pword)

pe:ge 'he went' (1 pword)

pe:k?e 'I'm going' (2 pwords--pe:k + e)

pe:ge? 'go!' (1 pword)

So it looks like glottal hiatus serves 2 roles--one of them marks word boundary.

1. it marks word-initial if the initial syllable is otherwise v-only

2. it prevents diphthongization within a word, even if it is across morpheme boundaries

I am not sure if this is a sufficient criterion for pword hood. It does not **DISTINGUISH** the start of the pword from the syllable (or boundaries).

3. "Rules" Part 2

Some rules referring to possible (and prohibited) syllable structures, processes of syllabification, and also to suprasegmental processes are sensitive to the domain of a phonologically independent unit. The distribution of these processes may help to define the boundaries and internal composition of such units.

Note:

--THE DEFAULT syllable template, and whether or not this template applies to the edges of phonologically free units. For example, a language may allow C clusters in coda position, but this may only happen at the ending edge of a phon. free unit, and not internally (or the other way around)

--C COMBOS—are the same types permitted both internally and at edges?

--syllabification patterns (across syllables internally, vs. across morphemes, vs. across independent units)

--SUPER heavy syllables (Hall 2001). Can something that is phonologically free end with a super-heavy syllable? Or can such syllables only be in an internal position? What are the types (e.g. CV:C; CVVC: CVCC)? Can all types occur *anywhere* in a phon. free unit? Note even any seemingly idiosyncratic restrictions (like, might a certain suffix never co-occur with a SHS?, etc.)

--STRESS It might be a good idea to look at stress rules first, as these can often clearly illuminate boundaries of phonologically free units—especially if the language only allows "1 main stress per word" or something of that nature. You can then work "backwards" and look at other cues to independent status.

--is there a primary stress rule? what is the domain?

--what types of forms are included, what is exempted?

--what are the minimal/maximal domains for stress to apply? Can a phonologically free unit that is simply (C)V take the main stress?

--can only lexical forms take a main stress, or can independent grammatical forms also take it?

--TONE Again, another good starting place if other cues are hard to find. Is the domain of tone a syllable? morpheme? phonologically free unit? If the language has syllabic tone, there may still be a word-level domain at work, like "only 1 high per phon. free unit" or something else like this. If grammatical forms take tone, do they also have other features that might suggest that they can stand alone phonologically (like the other stuff listed above)?

--"PITCH ACCENT" In some languages, the apparent tonal contrasts are not clearly defined until they occur on a "larger" unit. Describe the morphological and/or syllabic complexities of such units

4. Minimality & Maximality

Look at the grammar, look also at the dictionary/glossary entries if they are included. What is the most common (or only) minimal and maximal size of a phon. free unit? Or alternatively, what is the minimal/maximal morphological complexity/composition of something that is phonologically free? (C)V? CV (with an initial crucially present)? di- or polysyllable? How big can a free unit be in terms of syllable number? Do these size constraints apply only to lexical forms? If there are constraints, must a lexical form be bimorphemic to be free? If so, what morphemes qualify? Any & all?

Almost all words are CVC or di/polysyllabic. Only a couple of words are CV, and glottal juncture prevents V-only syllables and words. This suggests a bi-mora minimality constraint in Limbu.

5. Reduplication

Is the entire unit copied? More? Less? Can something of any phonological size/complexity have reduplication (even if the process is semantically restricted)? If there are different *types* of reduplication, see if you can find patterns, or note what the author says.

Is the resulting suprasegmental pattern of a reduplicated form the same or different from a single free form? (Are there 2 main stresses or 1? 2 tones? a different tone altogether?)

6. Other Questions

Note any discussion & descriptions of phonological boundaries attributed to interruption or pause phenomena. Also note if the author argues for boundaries because of repair phenomena. Examples. Only in the more detailed grammars will you probably see such discussions.

7. Phonological Units in Morphologically Complex Forms

--COMPOUNDING: note any patterns of segmental alteration with compounds—

especially at the edges of compounds; note prior and resulting stress/tone patterns; note segmental restrictions in compounds (e.g. in Manange, the 2nd element may never have an aspirated onset, even if the onset of the form when it is free is aspirated).

Again, note any conflicts of properties (e.g. in Lhasa Tibetan, a compound has 2 tone contours, but there is vowel harmony that spreads across the entire compound, and only a single main stress)

Sometimes in a compound, a piece of one of the elements may be deleted. If this happens, note any patterns, because this may suggest that one of the elements is in fact not a single phonological unit.

--"SIMPLE juxtaposition or concatenation of 2+ independent forms"—these are things that might be called "serialization" in some grammars: note any phonological discussion of these things. single tone? single stress? segment changes? ordering restrictions? co-occurrence restrictions?

No overt discussion of compounds in a phonological sense, but I gather that the remaining compound is 2 pwords because there are no segmental changes (well hardly any)

There is no discussion of stress in Limbu, so I cannot use that as evidence for or against.

Some compounds include:

phaksa 'pork' (phak 'pig' + sa 'meat')

wa?sa 'chicken meat' (wa? 'chicken' + sa 'meat')

mik-hi (his transcription) 'eye goo' (mik 'eye' + hi 'shit')

hukpho:nga 'handball/volleyball' (huk 'hand' + pho:ng 'kick') looks like final 'a' somehow added here? a nominalizer? not sure.

Sometimes there are a couple of segmental alterations, but no set pattern:

a final cons from first element may be lost and remainder undergoes place assim (1 example)

pitnu 'cow milk' (pi?l 'cow' + nu 'milk')

a glottal stop may be inserted (2 examples)

wetchya?dok 'cooked rice' (wetchya 'rice' + tok 'cooked grain')

looks like a voicing assim here too?

ha?lung 'fireplace stone' (ha 'tooth' + lung 'stone')

vD says this glottal is common at compound junctures, but not mandatory.

Current analysis:

compounds are 2 pwords because of no l~r alternation

some compounds show this alternation, but they may be acting more like a single pword. The semantics are specific Noun(instrument) + verb. In this case, the noun and the verbal prefixes seem to be phonologically cohering with the following verb stem.

ya-ke-rapt-u

blade-2-sharpen-ASP

'you sharpened it'

ya?-ke-rapt-u

paddy-2-dance/trample-ASP
'you paddy danced'

*These verbs are l-initial when not used in these types of constructions.
Also, the 'paddy dance' construction has different segments when used simply as a transitive construction:*

ya?-ke-lapt-u

paddy-2-dance/trample-ASP

'you trampled the paddy' (and not 'you paddy danced')

one exception:

sam + rippa

spirit + darken

'shade, shadow'

*vD analyzes the r-initial as the remnants of an old *kr cluster. This is a very old compound, and the rippa form never occurs alone (even with l-initial), and is not productive with other forms. This looks like a fused compound and a somewhat idiosyncratic exception to the l~r pattern that is otherwise pretty regular.*

--MULTI-morphemic forms: this is already discussed in above sections, but note especially phonologically free units that are minimally bimorphemic (or bigger), note any allomorphy that suggests that multi-morphemic forms behave as a single phonological unit.

There are a few disyllabic nominal and verbal suffixes. These include kusij or e:kke 'in the fashion of, like, as', taŋba 'like'

looking at one of these suffixes more closely: loʔrik quote marker

<i>'aŋga-ʔaŋ</i>	<i>pe:k-ʔε</i>	<i>ro:'</i>	<i>loʔr-ε</i>
<i>'I-too</i>	<i>go-1sPS/NPT</i>	<i>ASS</i>	<i>say-PT</i>

He said 'I'm coming too!' (224)

<i>huk-ʔo:</i>	<i>wa:p-mna-bε-n</i>	<i>mund-ε-rɔ</i>	<i>way-ε-i:</i>
<i>hand-LOC</i>	<i>wear-PP-NOM-ABS</i>	<i>work-PT-prG</i>	<i>be-PT-Q</i>

<i>mεm-mun-ʔe:</i>	<i>way-ε-i:'</i>	<i>loʔrik</i>	<i>se:ndo:s-u</i>
<i>npG-run-npG be-PT-Q</i>	<i>saying</i>	<i>ask-3P</i>	

'He asked him [saying], 'was the wristwatch running at the time or wasn't it?' (224)

There is the possibility that they are phonologically noncohering (separate) because of the l~r alternation pattern in suffixes that begin with /l/. They often have adverbial or attitudinal/epistemological functions in the clause, and many of them can be positioned clause finally (following the verb), or postposed to a noun. When following a noun, they have a slight meaning change, but often still convey adverbial, attitude or knowledge information. They might be their own phonological units, and possibly their own grammatical units too.

One exception

-lɔcə ~ -rɔcə

It's disyllabic but shows the alternations. It derives from a Nepali loan 'mirative', so there might be something special about its phonological behavior. Only Nepali loanwords can be r-initial in Limbu.

Also one monosyllabic particle that vD glosses as a particle (no bound morpheme marker)

Assertive lo: ~ ro:

*pe:g-aŋ lo:
go-1sPS/PT ASS
'I'm on my way!'*

*pe:g-i ro:
go-pADH ASS
'Come on, let's go!'*

These might be better analyzed as suffixes. They have a strict co-occurrence & ordering, and they show the l~r alternation. So, disyllabics are phonologically non-cohering, and monosyllabics are cohering.

--IF a language has a wide variety of inflectional affixes, do all stem-affix combinations have the same/similar stress, syllabification, segmental patterns, phon rules, tones, etc? Describe those that deviate from the set "general" patterns. Give examples. In German, for example, a stem + certain suffixes behaves as a **single** phonological unit ([li:.bɪ] 'love 1.sg'), but a stem + certain other suffixes behaves as **2** phonological units ([li:p.liç] 'dearly')—the resyllabification & voicing of the plosive is evidence of this.

The initial l~r alternations suggest that prefixes have a different phonological boundary than do (monosyllabic) suffixes.

This includes person marking prefixes on the verb and also the possessive prefixes on nouns.

Note the alternations between prefixes and suffixes:

Optative -lɔ ~ -rɔ (also Progressive function w/same alternations)

*khɛneʔ yəmba məna kɛ-bo:ŋ-lɔ
you big man 2-become-OPT
'May you become a great man' (133)*

*kusiŋ kɛ-ni:tt-u-rɔ!
understand 2-understand-3P-OPTlike.that 2-see-3p-OPT
'May you understand it! May you see it as it is!' (134)*

TIMES -lɛŋ ~ -rɛŋ

thik-lɛŋ

one-time
'once'

ŋi-rɛŋ
2-time
'twice'

GEN/ERG/INSTR

siŋbo:ŋ-le ku-bo:ŋ-ʔo:
tree-GEN its-base-LOC
'under the tree' (44)

anige-rɛ-n yaŋ
we-GEN-ABS money
'our money' (38)

syaʔ-lei:tt-u ...
jackal-ERG think-3P...
'The jackal thought...' (346)

saʔ-re suŋ me-daʔr-u-ba
child-ERG gift nsAS-bring-3P-IPF
'The children brought him a gift' (40)

a-mik-le
my-eye-INST
'with my eyes' (41)

thi:-llɛ ku-niŋ lɛʔ
millet.beer'-INST his-gall be.released
'He'll be fed up with millet beer' (42)

(note: there is an allomorph, a geminated e-llɛ or -llɛ version of these suffixes that surfaces with definite referents. No data with an indef-INST in grammar) Also, geminate /ll/ is distinct from /l/ and does not undergo the alternations that /l/ realizes.

Prefixed /l/-Initial Nouns

ku-
ku-lum-ʔo
its-between-LOC
'situated between' (359)

ku-le:dhi:mba

its-testicles
'his testicles' (363)

ku-laŋyo:p
its-footprint
'his footprint' (29)

with all other prefixes (*a-*, *ke-*, *aŋige-*, *khɛnchi-*, *khɛni-*, *khunchi-*), no data before *l-* initial nouns

Prefixed // -Initial Verbs

kɛ- (2nd psn)
ke-lept-u
2-throw-3P
'You threw it' (*M* handout)

Be sensitive to exceptions/variations in segmental/phonotactic, prosodic rules that may suggest that certain things "go together" phonologically, and others that do not. Explicitly state the conditions under which variations apply.

MORPHOLOGY & SYNTAX QUESTIONS

The goal here is to identify individual grammatical forms (or combinations of forms) as independent units (grammatical units/grammatical words). In some cases, these forms (or combinations of) exist as syntactic units, at other times as morphological units. Still other times, the distinctions will be collapsed or blurred. The primary interest here is not whether or not they are phonologically independent, although it is important to note whether or not the things you're describing are free or bound. This is because we will be creating a 3rd dedicated database that charts the overlaps/alignments between things that are phonologically free and things that are morpho-syntactically free.

8. Create a (glossed) list of inflectional morphemes (the types) described. Note the distribution of each morpheme:
 - with what **MUST** they co-occur (bound or free)?
 - with what else **MAY** they (optionally) co-occur (bound or free)?
 - if they co-occur with multiple different types of forms (either as a host or attached to a host), are the resulting meanings always the same, or are they different? Note the differences with examples.
 - can other elements ever be inserted between morphemae forms that comprise a stem + infl. form unit? See if adverbs can do this.

9. Note the overall constituent ordering patterns in the language. Is the pattern rigid, somewhat fluid, very fluid? Do all inflectional/grammatical elements that are called "free" follow the same ordering possibilities as lexical elements? Do they consistently appear in a single ordering scheme or co-occurrence scheme despite being phonologically independent. Pay special attention to so-called particles, or

other minimally free forms.

10. Does the author discuss grammatical forms/combinations with a conventionalized meaning or coherence? In other words, are there grammatical combinations with 1 meaning, and that meaning is lost or irretrievable (or totally different) when a piece of the form is missing or when the form is analyzed piece-by-piece? "Constructions" might be a way that grammarians describe this.

11. Are there elements with some degree of ordering or grammatical freedom, but that seem to be phonologically bound? Describe their distribution. Are there elements that appear to be phonologically independent (see above criterion), but have a fixed order or co-occurrence constraint? Describe these too. Pay special attention to things the author calls clitics.

12. Is a grammatical unit always bigger than a single morpheme? Always the same size? Are there some grammatical units that are a single morpheme, but others that are combinations? What is the biggest possible grammatical unit in the language (in terms of numbers of morphemes), and what is the smallest? Pay attention to, for example, the NP, and then also the elements that make up the NP. Then, note the predicate, and then the things that make up the predicate (may be called the "verbal complex").

13. Looking at the main verbal complex in the grammar, how morphologically complex is it? Looking at the predicate of the clause, how many verbs or verb-like elements must be present? verb-only? verb + aux form? 2 + verbs? If aux forms appear, is there a minimal amount (like, there must be at least 1 aux), or is there a maximal amount (like, there can be no more than 3...). In English, for example, in the predicate, there can be just 1 verb (=gword), but there can maximally be up to 1 verb plus 3 or so other gword forms (auxiliaries plus the main verb). (degree of synthesis)

